

Towards grassland biodiversity monitoring using AI-based pattern analysis on combined aerial and satellite imagery

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Abstract

Flanders has a highly fragmented landscape, where biodiversity is under threat. Grasslands are especially vulnerable, facing increasing pressure from agricultural intensification and competition from other land use types. Although systematic monitoring is essential, field-based surveys are too time- and resource-intensive for recurrent, area-wide application. Therefore, this study aims to investigate whether remote sensing and GeoAI techniques can complement fieldwork by helping to identify trends in biological value over larger areas and through time. AI-based pattern analysis is applied on a combination of aerial and satellite imagery to discriminate grasslands in terms of their restoration phase. Different setups are tested both with respect to inputs and classifiers. The obtained results, with test accuracies of up to 0.8, underline the potential of remote sensing to support grassland restoration monitoring at the regional scale.

Keywords: remote sensing, biodiversity, grasslands, pattern analysis

1. Introduction

The continuous pressure on open space poses a persistent threat to biodiversity, particularly in regions where natural areas are scarce and highly fragmented, such as Flanders. In order to protect and strengthen the remaining nature, a clear understanding of where biologically valuable areas occur and how they change over time is essential. Grasslands are especially vulnerable, facing increasing pressure from agricultural intensification and competition from other land use types. Although systematic monitoring is essential, field-based surveys are too time- and resource-intensive for recurrent, area-wide application. Therefore, this study aims to investigate whether remote sensing and GeoAI techniques can complement fieldwork by helping to identify trends in biological value over larger areas and through time, thereby supporting more effective nature conservation.

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2. Methodology

Bax and Schippers (1998) introduced the concept of grassland restoration phases and identified 6 phases that represent the transition from intensively cultivated to ecologically valuable grasslands. These different phases are described in terms of species composition but also general appearance and productivity, as shown in Table 1.

Table 1: Overview of the 6 grassland phases and their appearance, according to Zwaenepoel (2000).

Phase	Productivity (ton DM/ha/yr)	Description	Example
0 = ryegrass pasture	> 10	Dominance (>50%) of English ryegrass. Very uniform green appearance, almost only highly glossy grass.	
1 = grass mix	8-10	Coarse green patchwork quilt of different grasses with a few clustered patches of herbs.	
2 = dominant stadium	6-8	Dominance of mostly 1-2 grass species. Uniform color and structure (depending on dominant grass).	
3 = grass-herbs mix	5-7	Fine mosaic of thinner grasses and herbs, herbs uniformly spread.	
4 = flower-rich grassland	3-6	Similar to phase 3 but more flowers and stronger link to soil/moisture.	
5 = oligotrophic grasslands	< 5	Fine mosaic of sparser vegetation, rushes and sedges, yellow/gray/bluegreen colors, green-brown in winter.	

The overall objective of this study was to assess whether the different grassland phases can be distinguished using multi-source remote sensing, by leveraging the complementary strengths of aerial and satellite imagery. Over Flanders, high resolution aerial imagery is acquired yearly in winter and three-yearly in summer. These images were used to capture spatial patterns, such as colouring and texture at different scales. Moreover, using photogrammetry, a digital surface

model was derived, providing an estimation of the vegetation height when combined with the Digital Elevation Model Flanders. On the other hand, satellite image time series provide insight into the temporal dynamics, such as phenology, biomass accumulation and management practices like mowing. To capture this temporal dimension, we used satellite imagery acquired by the Copernicus programme, enhanced with the CropSAR AI fusion model. With its multispectral sensor, Sentinel-2 is perfectly suited to monitor vegetation dynamics. However, the presence of clouds hampers consistent monitoring. Sentinel-1 on the other hand carries a C-band SAR sensor that is not affected by clouds, but its observations are less directly linked to vegetation status. The CropSAR model exploits this complementarity, by fusing both through a set of ResNet blocks for encoding and decoding individual images, and a transformer encoder that explicitly focuses on the temporal dimension to perform the actual gap filling (Van Tricht et al., 2018; Van Tricht, 2023). This results in consistent and continuous time series of (optical) vegetation indices, like NDVI and FAPAR, as illustrated in Figure 1.

Figure 1: Example of CropSAR NDVI time series for a grassland parcel in 2024, as compared to the discontinuous Sentinel-2 observations.

In order to categorize the grasslands at the parcel level, a set of machine learning classifiers, including Random Forest (Breiman, 2001), CatBoost (Prokhorenkova et al., 2018), XGBoost (Chen & Guestrin, 2016) and LightGBM (Ke et al., 2017) were trained and their accuracy compared. A labeled reference dataset was compiled based on the Biological Valuation Map (*Biologische Waarderingskaart, BWK*) and Agricultural Parcels (*Landbouwgebruikspercelen*) datasets. From this dataset, stratified random samples of 5k and 1.5k fields were drawn for training and testing, respectively. The training dataset was further split into a training and validation dataset, following a 70-30% train-val split. Target labels were extracted by mapping the BWK units to the grassland restoration phase scheme. A hierarchical classification approach was used, with 4 levels ranging from a Level 1 classification, targeting two classes, to a Level 4 classification, targeting the individual grassland phases. Next to that, the separability of each phase (one vs. all) was investigated. In each of these setups, phases 1 and 2 were merged as the separation of these phases is not possible from the BWK-based classification scheme.

Input features were extracted from both the aerial imagery and the CropSAR time series for the period 2018-2024. However, first, a cleaning procedure was applied to mask out high vegetation

and buildings, cast shadows (from e.g. trees), permanent water bodies and parcel edges. From the yearly aerial images, GLCM-based (Gray-Level Co-occurrence Matrix) texture features (Haralick et al., 1973) were extracted at different scales, while for the CropSAR time series, both expert-based features and MiniRocket extracted features (Dempster et al., 2021) were compared.

3. Results

Figure 2 shows an overview of the obtained test accuracies across the tested feature space. These results underline the potential of remote sensing and geoAI models to support grassland biodiversity monitoring, with test accuracies up to 0.79 for Level 1 and 0.55 for Level 4. Phases 0 and 5 are the best distinguishable phases, with F1 scores up to 0.65 and 0.77 respectively. Combining the aerial and satellite imagery features clearly performs better than using either of the single data sources.

Figure 2: Boxplots of obtained test accuracies across the feature space for the different hierarchical classification levels (upper left) and individual phases (upper right), as well as a comparison of the obtained test accuracies across inputs (middle row) and classifiers (bottom row).

In terms of classifiers, Figure 3 illustrates that Random Forest is generally outperformed by the boosting models, with the highest accuracies obtained by CatBoost and XGBoost when targeting the single phases and hierarchical levels respectively. Adding the MiniRocket features generally leads to small gains in accuracy (2-4% except for phase F12 and F3, where we observe a drop of 1-3%).

Figure 3: Comparison of architectures and added value of MiniRocket feature for the different target classes (with combined inputs).

4. Conclusion and outlook

In this study, texture and surface height features derived from aerial imagery were combined with multispectral-radar fused satellite time series features in order to assess the grassland restoration phase of permanent grasslands. The results underline the potential of remote sensing and to support grassland biodiversity monitoring, with accuracies up to 0.79 for discriminating phase 0-2 from phase 3-5 and 0.55 for separating all individual phase classes. Accuracy-wise, the more recent boosting algorithms outperform Random Forest.

Future work includes an optimization of the multi-year aggregation strategy and the development of an associated uncertainty indicator, as well as further transferability testing based on recent fieldwork (from 2025) and a scaling-up of the model inference to the whole of Flanders. Ultimately, these maps will allow to detect areas with high nature value faster, as well as to estimate the speed of high nature value grassland restoration at the regional scale and link this to good practices of grassland management.

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